

Stability Constants of Bivalent Metal Chelates of N-Acetyl-N-p-Chlorophenylhydroxylamine

J. P. C. Jaimni and N. C. Sogani

Stabilities of palladium, copper, nickel, zinc and manganese chelates of N-acetyl-N-p-chlorophenylhydroxylamine in 70% v/v dioxan-water mixture have been determined by employing Bjerrum-Calvin pH titration technique. The titration medium was maintained at a constant ionic strength (0.1 M KCl) and at a temperature $25 \pm .5^\circ$ Log k, palladium 17.37, copper 17.14, nickel 11.08, zinc 9.53 and manganese 8.86.

N-Benzoyl-N-phenylhydroxylamine¹ (BPHA) is one of most interesting organic reagents reported recently. Besides BPHA, several derivatives and analogues of cupferron have been studied as possible analytical reagents²⁻⁴. A survey of literature revealed that stability of metal chelates of these compounds have not so far been studied. This was undertaken in these laboratories⁵. In the present communication the stabilities of bivalent metal chelates of N-Acetyl-N-p-chlorophenylhydroxylamine have been determined in 70% v/v dioxan-water mixture using Bjerrum-Calvin pH titration technique⁶. Titrations were carried out in duplicate using 40:1 ratio of chelating agents to metal ion concentration.

EXPERIMENTAL

N-Acetyl-N-p-chlorophenylhydroxylamine: The compound was prepared by adopting the method similar to that of Gupta and Sogani⁷ for the preparation of N-acetyl-N-phenylhydroxylamine. It is a new compound, m.p. 114° , yield 10.4 gms crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether mixture using p-chlorophenylhydroxylamine (4.3 gm) and acetylchloride (7.8 gms). Found: C, 51.58%; H, 4.29%; N, 7.51%; Cl, 19.00%. $C_8H_8NO_2Cl$ requires: C 51.7%; H, 4.34%; N, 7.54%; Cl, 19.08%.

A weighed amount of this compound was dissolved in 70% v/v dioxan-water mixture and diluted to give 0.04 M solution.

Standard palladium, copper, nickel, zinc and manganese solutions: Analytical grade of palladium chloride, copper chloride, nickel sulphate, zinc oxide and manganese chloride were used for preparing standard solutions. After standardising these solutions by usual classical methods, these were diluted to give 0.002 M solutions.

1. S. C. Shome, *Analyst*, 1950, **75**, 27.
2. G. D. Lutwick and D. E. Ryan, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1954, **32**, 949.
3. C. A. Armour and D. E. Ryan, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1957, **35**, 1454.
4. S. G. Tandon and S. C. Bhattacharyya, *J. Chem. Eng.*, 1962, *data 7*, pt. 2, 553.
5. J. P. C. Jaimni, Ph. D. Thesis (1966), University of Rajasthan, Jaipur.
6. M. Calvin and N. C. Melchior, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 3270.
7. H. K. L. Gupta and N. C. Sogani, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **37**, 769.

Sodium Hydroxide: Approximately 0.1 M carbonate free sodium hydroxide was prepared and standardised with analytical grade potassium hydrogen phthalate. It was diluted to give 0.02 M solutions.

Dioxan: The B. D.H. dioxan was purified by Weissberger's method⁸.

Potentiometric method: The pH titrations of the ligands with standard alkali solution in absence and in the presence of different metal ions were carried out by using Cambridge bench type pH meter which gives values accurate upto 0.02 pH unit. The pH meter was standardised before, and checked after, each titration with buffer solutions of pH 4.00 and 9.27. Electrode system consisted of glass electrode (pH range 1-13) and reference electrode as saturated calomel electrode.

10 ml. of 0.04 M ligand solution in 70% v/v dioxan were pipetted in a titrating vessel, requisite amount of 0.02M nitric acid was added to it, to lower the pH to about 2. The final ionic concentration was maintained at 0.1M by adding 5 ml. of 1M KCl. When titrating in presence of metal ions 5 ml. of 2×10^{-3} M metal ion solution were added at this stage. The total volume of the contents was made 50 ml. by adding varying amounts of dioxan and distilled water in such proportions that it finally became 70% v/v dioxan-water mixture. It was titrated against 0.02M NaOH. The temperature of the solution was maintained at $25 \pm 0.5^\circ$. The pH meter readings obtained at a given alkali addition in duplicate titrations were reproducible with a maximum variation of ± 0.02 pH unit. The titration curves are shown in fig. 1.

Calculations: The horizontal distance between the reference titration curve and the curve obtained in presence of a metal ion gives the amount of metal bound ligand. This value divided by the total metal ion concentration gives \bar{n} . In this way the values of \bar{n} at different pH values were calculated.

TABLE I

Stabilities of metal chelates of N-Acetyl-N-p-chlorophenylhydroxylamine

Metal ion	log k_1	log k_2	log $k_1 k_2$
Palladium	9.63	7.74	17.37
Copper	9.57	7.57	17.14
Nickel	6.16	4.92	11.08
Zinc	5.16	4.37	9.53
Manganese	4.89	3.97	8.86

At any pH value of free ligand concentration (A^-) was calculated from the total ligand concentration, HA. and its ionisation constant. This is based on the assumption that the amount of chelating agent over metal ion is so great that the removal of HA by chelation does not cause any significant change in the equilibrium: $HA \rightleftharpoons H^+ + A^-$. The pKa value of N-acetyl-N-p-chlorophenylhydroxylamine was potentiometrically found to be 10.91.

In calculating the values for \bar{n} and (A^-), the concentrations were corrected for changes in volume, produced by addition of alkali during titrations. In this way a series of values

for \bar{n} and (A^-) corresponding to the different values of pH , was obtained. The formation curves of metal chelates of N-acetyl-N-p-chlorophenylhydroxylamine are shown in Fig. 2.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

The values of $\log k_1$, $\log k_2$, and $\log k_1 k_2$ for various metal chelates were read directly from the formation curves and are given in Table 1.

DISCUSSION

The consumption of alkali during the course of titration can be due to the ligand, the hydrolysis of metal ion and the ligand protons liberated in complex formation.

The ligand under study is a very weak acid ($pK_a=10.91$). Thus the ligand protons as such are not in a titrable form. Hydrolyses of these metal ions in 70% dioxan water mixture have been studied⁹ and are not likely to interfere in the stability determinations. Moreover, there was no precipitation during the chelation titrations, ruling out the possibility of hydrolysis of these metal ions in presence of large excess of ligands. Thus, the consumption of an excess alkali in chelation over the simple ligand titration is due to the ligand protons liberated during the complex formation. This may be represented as:

The following order of stability of N-acetyl-N-p-chlorophenylhydroxylamine metal chelates was found—palladium > copper > nickel > zinc > manganese.

The authors express their gratitude to Prof. R. C. Mehrotra for providing facilities in the department. They are also grateful to the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi for granting a research fellowship to one of them (J. P. C. Jaimni).

CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
UNIVERSITY OF RAJASTHAN,
JAIPUR, INDIA.

Received, March 20, 1967.